

Effect of Psychological Well-Being, Compensation, and Physical Work Environment towards Employee Satisfaction at PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to test and analyze the effect of psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment towards employee satisfaction at PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan. This type of research is causal research with a quantitative approach. This research uses a method of saturated samples, i.e. all employees amounting to 33 people are used as samples of research. The analysis of this study used multiple linear regression. Results showed that simultaneously psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment have significant effect on employee satisfaction at PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan. Partial psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment positively and significantly effect on employee satisfaction. Compensation is a more dominant factor effect on employee satisfaction. PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan should increase compensation and pay attention to employee satisfaction, so that employees work better.

Keywords: Psychological Well-Being, Compensation, Physical Work Environment, Employee Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

In the modern era, managing workers becomes difficult because employees know their rights as employees when they work. Therefore, it is important that companies identify employee needs and

employee satisfaction in ensuring the achievement of organizational objectives and objectives effectively. Employee satisfaction is essentially something that is a masterpiece. Each employee has a different level of satisfaction according to the value system that applies to him (Rivai & Sagala, 2013).

According to Blum in (Tanujaya, 2014) and Robbin in (Wibowo, 2016) defines employee satisfaction as a whole result of the degree of dislike or dislike of employees on various aspects of his work, self-adjustment and social relations of employees outside of work. Employee satisfaction is also interpreted as a general attitude towards a person's work indicating the difference between the number of awards received by the worker and the amount that the worker believed should be acceptable.

Employee satisfaction can be assessed by many factors, including psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment.

According to Rivai & Sagala (2013) Compensation is something that employees receive as a substitute for employee service contributions to the company. Compensation to employees, not just actions for money or facilities, but is an action that must be well planned, integrated, and comprehensive to be able to be a driver of the high spirit of work to all employees.

According to Syahreza et al. (2017) Compensation has a high effect on the retention of employees because with satisfactory compensation, employees will feel that the company cares about the needs of employees. According to Wibowo (2016) mistakes in implementing the reward system will lead to demotivation and absence of satisfaction among workers. Therefore, employee satisfaction will produce employees who work optimally according to the wishes of the company.

The work environment is also one of the factors that can affect employee satisfaction in achieving the company's objectives. According to Sutrisno (2010) Work environment is the whole facilities and infrastructures that exist around the employees who can influence the implementation of the work. This work environment includes workplace, facilities and work aids, cleanliness, lighting, tranquility, as well as working relationship between the people in the place. According to Sedarmayanti (2011) An employee is able to perform a good job when supported by a suitable working environment. Good or suitable working environment, if employees can carry out their work optimally, healthy, safe and comfortable. According to Lubis et al. (2019) The working environment is an image of the reality of the work world. The work environment provides information about the lives of employees who come to work, gather for the same purpose, and carry out the work in the company's rules.

In general, the working environment consists of a physical work environment and a non-physical work environment. The working environment referred to in the study is focused on the physical state of the workplace. With a good physical work environment, employees can work well, safely, and comfortably without any interference such as improper temperatures, noisy sound, less or greater illumination, and other distractions. Every company is obliged to provide a good physical work environment for employees to create employee satisfaction from their work, so

that employees will maintain high working performance, and optimal performance (Sedarmayanti, 2011).

The company where the research was conducted at PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan, is one of the companies engaged in the textile industry and produces uniform garments in Medan city. In order to survive, the company is required to always have good performance and maintain the product quality. To acquire employees who work well, the fundamental thing to do is to give the employee satisfaction first. Psychological well-being factors, compensation and physical work environment are some factors to be considered by the company in giving employee's employee satisfaction.

Employee satisfaction could affect the company's performance and employee satisfaction has a positive impact on the company's performance (Quilim et al., 2016). Problems in employee satisfaction are evident from the company's unrealized sales targets. Based on employee work satisfaction will be reflected in how performance is generated by employees in completing their duties and obligations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Psychological Well-Being

According to Ryff in (Tanujaya, 2014) There are several factors that affect the psychological well-being, among others:

1. Age

Some of the PWB's dimensions such as environmental mastery and self-autonomy tend to increase with increasing age, especially when moving from a young adult to a medium adult period. Other dimensions such as personal development and life objectives tend to decline as we age, especially from intermediate adulthood to advanced age.

2. Gender

In his research expressed gender differences affecting the dimensions of psychological well-being. It is found that women of all ages tend to have high scores on the dimension of positive relationships with

others and personal development when compared to men.

3. Socio-Economic Status

From research it is known that high psychological well-being (especially in the dimension of life purpose and personal development) is found in employees who have a high level of education. High psychological well-being is also found in employees who have high employment status.

4. The Culture

From research results on the psychological well-being performed in South Korea shows that respondents in South Korea have higher scores on the dimension of positive relationships with others and lower scores on self-acceptance dimensions. It is caused by a more collective cultural orientation and interdependence.

5. The Personality

Employees who have personal and social competence, such as self-acceptance, able to establish a harmonious relationship with the environment, skills coping with (coping with skills) are effective to avoid conflict and stress.

2.2 Compensation

According to Rivai & Sagala (2013), the compensation program reflects the efforts that the company takes to retain its employees. Compensation to employees, not just actions for money or facilities, but is an action that must be well planned, integrated, and comprehensive to be able to be a driver of the high spirit of work to all employees. According to Syahreza et al. (2017) Compensation has a high effect on the retention of employees because with satisfactory compensation, employees will feel that the company cares about the needs of employees. Therefore, compensation needs to be managed in such a way as to function effectively and efficiently. Effective in question is that compensation given to employees is able to meet the needs of employees so that employees are eager to work, but on the other hand, the expenditure of expenses by the Organization as

compensation should not be a heavy burden for the organization.

2.3 Physical Work Environment

According to Sutrisno (2010), the work environment is the whole facilities and infrastructures that exist around the employees who are doing the work that can affect the implementation of the work. This work environment includes workplace, facilities and tools of work, cleanliness, lighting, tranquility, as well as the working relationship among the people in the place. In general, the working environment consists of a physical work environment and a non-physical (psychic) work environment.

2.4 Employee Satisfaction

There are several reasons why companies should pay attention to employee satisfaction. According to Robbins & Judge (2015) There are six benefits employees work satisfaction for the company include:

1. Employee Performance

An employee with a high level of satisfaction will have good performance, and this will have an impact on the organizational performance.

2. Organizational Behaviour

Satisfied employees tend to speak positively about the company where it works, and employees will also do more in the work.

3. Customer Satisfaction

Employees who feel satisfied tend to be more friendly, cheerful, and responsive to customers, employees who are satisfied not easy to change work, most likely customers will meet familiar faces and receive services from experienced employees, this quality will build customer satisfaction and loyalty.

4. Employee Attendance

The reason this can be accepted is very reasonable when dissatisfied employees tend to neglect jobs, this is more compounded with the absence of the employee because it tends to be lazy to carry out their work.

5. Employee Turnover

Employees who are satisfied will not show the behaviour to leave the

organization/company, including finding new positions and resigning.

6. Deviant Behaviour in The Workplace
Work dissatisfaction tends to lead to an employee's specific behaviour, such as union-forming efforts, misuse of authority, and even theft.

RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Types and Properties of Research

The type of research used is causal research with a quantitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2012) A causal study with a quantitative approach is a study aimed at testing theories, building facts, showing relationships between variables, providing statistical descriptions, attracting and predicting the results with the intention of knowing the effect between variables of one with the other variables. The research aims to illustrate the psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment towards employee satisfaction at PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan.

3.2 Location and Research Time

This research was conducted at PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan, located in Jalan Prof. H. M Yamin, S. H No. 8, Kesawan, Medan-West. Research time from November 2019 to May 2020.

3.3 Population and Samples

The population in this study was all employees of PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan with a population size of 33 people. Using the sampling technique is a saturated sample, the entire population will be used as a sample because the population is less than 30 people. The research samples were obtained from PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan employees as many as 33 respondents.

3.4 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Methods

The method of double linear regression analysis used by researchers is to find out how much free variable influence is the psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment of the bonded variable that is employee satisfaction then to answer the hypothesis.

RESULT

Partial Testing (t Test)

Partial testing (t test) or test is partially used to test partial influence between free variables, i.e., psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment of the bonded variable, i.e. employee satisfaction. According to Table 1 you can explain that:

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	17.235	7.261		2.374	.024
	Psychological Well-Being	.296	.125	.282	2.370	.025
	Compensation	.334	.096	.380	3.471	.002
	Physical Work Environment	.279	.084	.350	3.313	.002
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Satisfaction						
Source: Research Result, 2020 (Processed Data)						

1. Psychological well-being has a value $t_{count} > t_{table}$ this $2.370 > 2.03$ with a significant value of $0.025 < 0.05$, if psychological well-being increases, it will increase employee satisfaction. Conversely, if psychological well-being is declining, employee satisfaction will decrease.

2. Compensation has a value $t_{count} > t_{table}$ this $3.471 > 2.03$ with a significant value of $0.002 < 0.05$, if compensation increases, it will increase employee satisfaction. Conversely, if compensation is declining, employee satisfaction will decrease.

3. Physical work environment has a value $t_{count} > t_{table}$ this $3.313 > 2.03$ with a significant value of $0.002 < 0.05$, if physical work environment increases, it will increase employee

satisfaction. Conversely, if physical work environment is declining, employee satisfaction will decrease.

Simultaneous Testing (F Test)

The results of F test can be seen in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2: Simultaneous Testing (F Test) Results ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	428.145	3	142.715	122.688	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.734	29	1.163		
	Total	461.879	32			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Satisfaction
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Psychological Well-Being, Compensation, Physical Work Environment
 Source: Research Result, 2020 (Processed Data)

Table 2 shows the value of $F_{count}=122.688$ and $f_{table}=2.93$ thus $F_{count} >$ with the value of significance 0.000 is smaller than the alpha value 0.05, then the decision taken is H_0 rejected and H_1 accepted. That is, psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment simultaneously have significant effect on employee satisfaction.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Results showed that simultaneously psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment have significant effect on employee satisfaction at PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan. Partial psychological well-being, compensation and physical work environment positively and significantly effect on employee satisfaction.

Based on the above conclusion, some advice given as input and evaluation material for the company as well as for further researchers who want to develop similar research include foror PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan to be able to realize the difficult sales target, the company should pay attention to the level of employee work satisfaction. The problematic work satisfaction condition resulted in employees being indifferent to the company so that the company had difficulty in achieving the targets to be achieved. For that, a few things to note regarding employee work satisfaction through:

1. Psychological well-being welfare of employees is enhanced through self-motivation trainings so that employees can

become better employees of their psychologically. The company leadership also has an important role to provide motivation and attention to employees through non-formal activities such as sharing or counseling to provide advice and feedback to employees who are in trouble.

2. Compensation which is the dominant factor in employee satisfaction work should be a more concern for the company. One of the ways that can be done by raising employee salaries annually or providing bonuses to employees who have good job achievements. This at once will spur the employee's morale towards a better one. Related to health insurance and incentive for employees, the company can increase the cost of liability for insurance and incentives so that employees are satisfied with the compensation given by the company.

3. Physical work environment should be considered especially on work room layout issues. Flexible workspace layouts can create a more comfortable atmosphere when working. Incomplete work equipment problems can be solved by often examining the willingness of the work equipment so as not to become an employee's obstacle when completing the work. Lighting less room can be added more in some side of the office that needs more light. Provide deodorizer and maintain office cleanliness to be a solution that can be done to create the scent of room that relax the mind of the employees. Hot air circulation can be designed cooler by adding air conditioner so that employees do not overheat. An important role leader who cares about the

employee's condition is indispensable for the company.

For employees of PT. Gracia Multi Moda Medan, it is hoped that employees are more critical and brave to communicate with leaders related to the problems faced in the work. Employee satisfaction is expected to not reduce employees' working spirit in completing tasks and responsibilities in a timely manner.

For researchers furthermore, a few things to note is that the sample size of the research is too small to be a certain limitation in this study. Research on the psychological well-being variables of the relatively few employee satisfaction is also a challenge for this research so it is hoped to find a lot of reference sources.

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